

Some important practical aspects of the NFDI4Cat ontology and metadata design

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NFDI4Cat is one of the NFDI consortia, which targets research data management for catalysis-related sciences. The initial outcome of this project with respect to the architecture and interoperability requirements was obtained in the course of user interviews, collecting competency questions, and exploring the landscape of semantic artefacts [1,2]. Despite of the numerous efforts in the development of metadata standards and domain ontologies, the advantages offered by an optimal interplay between them for the implementation of FAIR principles seem not to be well understood yet.

In this work general aspects of the metadata and ontology organization are considered and applied to some typical research steps in chemistry and spectroscopy. For representing the metadata a prototype ontology is built. In general, it should be metadata-centered, suitable for the description of research workflows in experimental chemistry and spectroscopy, involve all relevant semantic artefacts for searching metadata, and, in particular, enable semantic search according to workflow patterns. In the current implementation these features are based on a model representation of a general research workflow in experimental chemistry and spectroscopy. By construction, the corresponding vocabulary can be to a great extent easily subordinated to overarching ontologies like BFO [3] and Metadata4Ing [4], which makes it compatible with other standards.

The last but not the least, it is demonstrated how properly structured class hierarchies and relations can unequivocally shape the acquisition of required metadata in a systematic way, and make it only loosely coupled with the nature of the metadata. To the best of my knowledge, this aspect of the ontology design has not been considered in much detail. On contrary to this approach, the amount and quality of metadata created based exclusively on a top-level ontology seem to be very subjective.

The metadata for a given research step are encapsulated within a so-called metaset, that is a collection of the corresponding metadata files organized into a separate folder. The metadata are stored within the RDF data model using Turtle (XML) serialization. Metasets are organized as an additional independent layer to existing data infrastructure. Each metaset has its own URI that is based on an overarching (institutional) URI. At the same time, the URI of a metaset provides the base URI for the corresponding local resources. Published metasets can be hyperlinked by appropriate software via common URIs. This can be done by introducing hyperlinks on top of the Turtle serialization, or transforming the latter into an informal hypertext. This would provide highly-intuitive means for navigating and understanding various resources, which is more convenient than the application of the query protocol such as SPARQL. These and other possibilities for the lookup of metadata can be very practical. In principle, it implies the Electronic Lab Notebook functionality for searching and accessing various information resources which is invariant with respect to the scaling of the scope from a local group to an overarching inter-institutional level. Such an invariance could have a huge impact on the global acceptance of the proposed approach in the community.

References

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